

OBTAINING A FUNCTIONAL IMPRESSION DURING PROSTHETICS OF PARTIAL ADENTIA**Arkhmammadov A.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, associate professor
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Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7621350>**Abstract**

Functional impressions are widely used in prosthetics of patients with complete loss of teeth. However, the advantages of a functional impression over an anatomical one turned out to be so obvious and effective that this was the reason for the development of a technique for obtaining it in patients with partial loss of teeth:

- a) a functional impression allows you to determine the optimal relationship between the edge of the base of the prosthesis and the adjacent soft tissues;
- b) it contributes to better fixation and stabilization of a partial removable denture;
- c) it provides a more rational distribution of masticatory pressure between different parts of the prosthetic bed;
- d) it can provide the necessary compression of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, corresponding to the masticatory pressure.

Keywords: individual tray, functional cast, Partial edentulous.

The impression is an information link between the doctor and the dental technician, and the accuracy of the impression largely determines the quality of orthopedic treatment. Currently, one-piece cast combined (consisting of fixed and removable parts) prostheses are widely used. Their production is traditionally carried out in two stages. At the first stage, a fixed part of the cast structure is made to obtain a refined impression and a working model cut into fragments. On such a model it is impossible to make a removable part. In addition, when taking an impression, the underlying soft tissues of the prosthetic bed are pressed out, which leads to their distortion. Therefore, after the manufacture of a non-removable structure, the stage of re-obtaining an impression and manufacturing a new working model with a non-removable part installed on it is mandatory. Such a repetition of the clinical and laboratory stages is inconvenient, stretched in time and requires an increase in the number of visits to the dental clinic by the patient.

PURPOSE OF THE WORK

In connection with the foregoing, there was a need for a method for obtaining an impression simultaneously for both the fixed and removable parts of the combined prosthesis. The impression in this case should perfectly display the elements of the abutment teeth, the gingival margin and the ledge, the relief of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed and the functional state of the mobile tissues of the oral cavity adjacent to the prosthesis. This can be solved by taking an impression using an individual tray [1].

The variety of clinical situations encountered in the oral cavity dictates the need for a differentiated approach to the choice of material and technique for obtaining an impression. Traditionally, for the treatment of patients with modern one-piece cast constructions, methods are used: two-layer one-stage, one-layer one-stage, injector, etc. [3] But they all involve the use of standard spoons. Individual ones are traditionally used in the treatment of complete absence of teeth. However, in the case of treating patients with combined structures, it becomes necessary to transfer the functional state of the tissues of the prosthetic bed, which is possible only when using an individual spoon [5]. Therefore, we have proposed a method for obtaining a refined impression using an individual spoon in the orthopedic treatment of partial absence of teeth.

RESEARCH METHOD

To create a uniform layer of impression material, we perform isolation with a base wax plate (thickness 2 mm). To create a differentiated pressure on the tissues of the prosthetic bed, we make perforations in an individual spoon. We make an individual spoon on a diagnostic plaster model with a drawing of the future design.

We outline the boundaries of the individual spoon: from the vestibular side in the region of the supporting teeth and the edentulous alveolar process along the transitional fold, bypassing the frenulum of the lips and the bands of the buccal mucosa, in the remaining teeth at the level of the necks; on the oral side - on the upper jaw it covers the entire sky, on the lower one - in the region of the edentulous part of the alveolar process and

supporting teeth, it passes along the transitional fold, and in the remaining teeth below the level of the necks by 10-15 mm. Then we outline the "contact zones", retreating from the border of the prosthesis by 2-3 mm, and "stop points". "Stop points" are specially created contacts in the area of the edentulous part of the alveolar process of the jaw. They are necessary for the orientation of the spoon on the tissues of the prosthetic field, which is carried out by contact of its inner surface with areas free from elements of the future prosthesis, or with "stop points". Next, we isolate the undercuts of the teeth and the alveolar process with wax / Compress the softened base wax plate (2 mm) over the entire surface of the model. The areas of "contact zones" and "stop points" are cut out. We add wax to the model.

Spoons are made from self-hardening plastic or by light curing from a glass-containing composite using traditional methods.

To obtain an impression, we fit an individual tray in the patient's mouth, specifying the boundaries and correct location on the prosthetic bed. The edge of an individual spoon in the area of the edentulous part of the alveolar process is formed using Herbst's samples. In the area of "contact zones" and "stop points" in the spoon, we make holes for the purpose of decompression in these areas. We carry out the expansion of the gingival sulcus to provide horizontal and vertical access to the impression material and to prevent bleeding and reduce the release of gingival fluid. Next, we apply an impression mass on the dried gingival sulcus and teeth from a special syringe. At the same time, the doctor's assistant prepares and places the same material in the individual impression tray. Then the spoon is inserted into the mouth and centered. With the help of passive and active movements with soft tissues, we shape the edges of the impression and then hold the impression on the prosthetic bed without pressure.

The manufacturing technology of a combined denture in one impression can be considered complete only if techniques are used for the manufacture of the model, when the interdental papillae are not destroyed during the processing of the model, the level and volume of the gums are preserved, for example, Modell-Tray [2]. The use of an individual tray in the treatment of partial absence of teeth, in combination with a correctly selected impression material, allows obtaining differentiated pressure on various parts of the prosthetic bed, functionally designing the edge of the artificial base of the removable part of the prosthesis, and reducing the adaptation time [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As an example. Patient A., aged 50, applied to the clinic of the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, a patient at the age of 50 complained of missing teeth, difficulty chewing food and an aesthetic defect. Based on the survey data, a treatment plan was drawn up: to make a combined prosthesis for the upper jaw, consisting of: a fixed part - bridge-like metal-ceramic prostheses and with a patric part of the locking system of fixation; the removable part is a clasp prosthesis with a locking fixation system. For the manufacture of a high-quality prosthesis, the patient needs to obtain an accurate imprint of the supporting teeth, gingival margin and ledge,

the relief of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed and the functional state of the mobile oral tissues adjacent to the prosthesis, so we use an individual spoon. The technique for obtaining an impression is a one-stage single-phase with retraction of the gingival margin. The impression material can be a silicone material of group A-silicones of a liquid consistency.

The treatment was carried out according to the generally accepted method. Received a diagnostic model. Using a parallelometer, the structural features of the prosthesis were determined. Teeth were prepared for the manufacture of ceramic-metal bridges, and temporary dentures were made on the same visit. Further, on a diagnostic plaster model with a drawing of the future design, the boundaries of the individual spoon, the "contact zone" and the "stop points" were outlined, departing from the border of the prosthesis by 2-3 mm. We make an individual rigid spoon from self-hardening plastic according to the traditional method, with a thickness of at least 2-3 mm. On the next visit, an individual spoon was placed in the patient's mouth, specifying the boundaries and correct location on the prosthetic bed. The edge of an individual tray in the region of the edentulous part of the alveolar process was formed using Herbst's samples. And in the area of "contact zones" and "stop points" holes were made in the spoon. The impression was obtained by a one-stage single-phase technique. Retraction - by mechano-chemical method using a retraction thread impregnated with a buffer solution of aluminum chloride. The impression material was brought with a syringe to the gingival grooves and abutment teeth. A collapsible combined model was made. The model was obtained with the preservation of the level and volume of the gums. This model is working for the manufacture of both fixed and removable parts of the prosthesis. Next, a combined prosthesis was made according to the traditional method. During the manufacture of the removable part, the canopy was isolated on the vestibular slope in the frontal area using a light-cured composite.

When fitting and applying the prosthesis, there were no difficulties and the need for correction

The patient was scheduled for examination on the 10th day after fixation of the prosthesis. There were no complaints. On examination, the prosthesis is adjacent to the surface of the prosthetic bed, and is stable during function. There are no signs of trauma or inflammation on the mucous membrane. Analysis of the results of treatment of the patient within one year showed the effectiveness of the treatment. X-ray and clinical control confirmed the high-quality fitting of the structure and the absence of pathological changes in the area of the preserved teeth. The patient is quite satisfied with the restoration of functions and aesthetic requirements.

Conclusion

Thus, obtaining an impression in the treatment of partial absence of teeth with combined solid-cast prostheses, in combination with a correctly selected impression material, allows obtaining differentiated pressure on various parts of the prosthetic bed, functionally shaping the edge of the artificial base of the removable

part of the prosthesis, reducing the duration of adaptation and, in general, increasing quality of orthopedic treatment.

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